

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№6(1)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 448 sahifa,
1-iyun, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Woogyu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Doniyorov S. M. – "Yangi O'zbekiston" va "Pravda Vostoka" gazetalari tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (Phd)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the DM Editorial Office of the newspapers “Yangi O'zbekiston” and “Pravda Vostoka”, Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology, Associate Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi” jurnali O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Milliy xarakter tushunchasining pedagogik va aksiologik talqini.....	10
<i>Usmonova Muattar Bahadirjonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning o'zini o'zi anglashida muloqotning o'rni	14
<i>Yaxshiboyeva Zuhra, Pardayeva Munisa</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida sog'lom turmush tarzi ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning zamonaviy usullari	17
<i>Dilsora Shodmonova</i>	
Педагогические предпосылки развития билингвизма у детей в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях	24
<i>Истамова Нигора Азимжановна</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida neyrogimnastika texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning pedagogik asoslari.....	29
<i>Saidova Nigora Olimovna, G'ulomova Shaxnoza Abdusalom qizi</i>	
Jismoniy tarbiya va sport: iqtidorli yoshlarni tanlash, saralash va ularni maqsadli tayyorlashning zamonaviy yo'llari.....	32
<i>Muxamedjanov Shovkat Muxrumovich</i>	
Yoshlar ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyasida tarixiy xotira, milliy meros va qadriyatlardan foydalanishning pedagogik asoslari.....	36
<i>Nomozov Muhammadyusuf Meyliqul o'g'li</i>	
Sport tashkilotlarida rahbarlik qilish va boshqarish.....	40
<i>Artikov Xayrulla Baxtiyarovich</i>	
Formation and Development Stages of Terminology as a Scientific Discipline	44
<i>Lola Mannobova</i>	
Lexicographic Features of Onomastic Units in English and Uzbek Dictionaries	48
<i>Berdiyeva Mashhura Tulqin qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining qobiliyat, qiziqish va o'rganish usullarini hisobga olgan pedagogik metodlar va dars rejaları	51
<i>Abdullaeva Gulmira, Egamberganova Yorqinoy Ollobergan qizi</i>	
Disputning ingliz romanlaridagi pragmatik va lingvokulturologik ko'rinishlari	55
<i>Abdumalikova Diyoraxon Rafiqjon qizi</i>	
O'yin texnologiyalarining aqliy rivojlanishida muammolari bo'lgan bolalar ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni	59
<i>Abdunazarov Abdumutal Olimovich</i>	
Auditoriyada va auditoriyadan tashqari jarayonda talabalar ijtimoiylashuvini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari	64
<i>Alimova Gulrux Farhod qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kreativ fikrlashni rivojlantirishda interaktiv o'yin texnologiyalarining pedagogik imkoniyatlari	70
<i>Axtamova Mohinur O'tkir qizi</i>	
Oilaviy zo'ravonlikka uchragan ayollarni qo'llab-quvvatlashda mahalla va ijtimoiy xizmatlarning o'rni	74
<i>Dumarova Gulfira Kozimbekovna, To'liqinova Muxlisaxon Jamshid qizi</i>	
O'zbek milliy romanchiligida tarixiy haqiqat va badiiy talqin (Xayriddin Sultonning "Yaldo kechasi" romani misolida)	78
<i>G'aybulloyeva Parvina Samandar qizi</i>	
Aqli zaif bolalarda kommunikativ faoliyatning ontogeneza shakllanishi	82
<i>Hamraqulova Durdona Dilshod qizi</i>	
Neuroeducation va Phygital Learning asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kognitiv faolligini rivojlantirish metodikasi	87
<i>Hikmatova Yulduz Nuritdinovna</i>	

Autizm spektri buzilgan bolalarning ijtimoiy-pedagogik moslashuvining nazariy asoslari	91
<i>Shodmanxojiyeva Iroda Ne'matulla qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda nutq rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlashda o'yin texnikalarining roli	95
<i>Jamolova Farida Fatillo qizi</i>	
Ta'lim qardosh tillarga yo'naltirilgan mtt direktorining boshqaruv kompetentligini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari (Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi misolida)	98
<i>Jumagulova Gulziya Madiyarovna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda talabalarning raqamli taqdimot va ommaviy nutq ko'nikmalarini axborot texnologiyalari vositasida takomillashtirish	103
<i>Junaydullayev Oxunjon Kaxorjon o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida o'yin texnologiyalari orqali nutq malakalarini rivojlantirish	107
<i>Maqsuda Maxsudovna Murodova</i>	
O'zbek tilida "nur" so'zining ko'chma ma'nolari	113
<i>Maxbuba Axatova</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiya fani o'qituvchilarini kasbiy tayyorlashda raqamli texnologiyalar va interfaol metodlardan foydalanishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	116
<i>Misirova Nodira Tovbayevna, Nosirova Dilfuza Sa'dullayevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ingliz tilida og'zaki nutqini shakllantirishdagi qiyinchiliklar	120
<i>Nabiyeva Xilola Abdulmuratovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning ma'naviy-ma'rifiy qiyofasini shakllantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari... ..	123
<i>Niyozova Maftuna Normaxmat qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida "Tarbiya" fanini tabiiy fanlar bilan integratsiyalash asosida ekologik tafakkurni shakllantirish.....	126
<i>Norbo'tayeva Iroda Yunusovna</i>	
Suzish vositalari yordamida talabalarning qo'l va oyoq mushaklarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	130
<i>Nosirov Sardor To'lqinjon o'g'li</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarning metakognitiv kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning didaktik imkoniyatlari	134
<i>Nosirova Ra'no Xamidovna</i>	
Dual ta'limda oliy ta'lim va maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari o'rtasidagi hamkorlikning mazmuni.....	137
<i>Qoraboyeva Zohidaxon To'lanboyevna, Tursunbayeva Sevara Abdullo qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi bolalar nutqida noverbal vositalarning roli.....	142
<i>Qurbanova Surayyo Tuynazar qizi, Maqsudboyeva Dilbar Olimjon qizi</i>	
Texnologiya fanini o'qitishda integrativ yondashuvning pedagogik zarurati va nazariy asoslari	146
<i>Qurbonmurotov Eldor Abdusaidovich</i>	
O'zbekistonning zamonaviy ta'lim muhitida o'zbek-rus bilingvizmi sharoitida o'quvchilar nutqining psixolingvistik xususiyatlari.....	149
<i>Qurdasheva Bonu Bexzod qizi</i>	
Xorij olimlari tadqiqotlarida prosotsial xulq-atvor namoyon bo'lishining o'rganilishi	153
<i>Rahimova Sarvinoz Odilboy qizi</i>	
Musiqqa fanlarini o'qitishda inquire-based learning texnologiyasidan foydalanish metodlari.....	157
<i>Raximova Dilbar Rizakulovna</i>	
Maktab rahbarining qaror qabul qilish uslubi pedagogik jamoa ijtimoiy faolligini rivojlantirish omili sifatida..	161
<i>Raximova Maryam O'tkir qizi</i>	
Yosh sportchilarda yurak-qon tomir tizimining morfofunksional adaptatsiyasi va sportchi yuragi fenomeni..	173
<i>Alimova Nasiba Adxamovna</i>	
Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyotda turizm klasterlarini rivojlantirishning zamonaviy yo'nalishlari.....	179
<i>Kurbonova Kamola Ilxomovna</i>	
Nutq madaniyati va notiqlik san'ati	183
<i>Mamadaliyeva Lola Shailyasovna</i>	
Molekulyar fizikada klasster yondashuvi asosida masalalar yechish samaradorligini oshirish	188
<i>Mirzamuratov Baxodir Fayzullayevich</i>	
Oliy o'quv yurtlari, sport tashkilotlari va sport marketingi tashkilotlari o'rtasidagi hamkorlikning zarurati.....	192
<i>Samatov Javlonbek Abdukayumovich</i>	

Bo'lajak biologiya o'qituvchilarida tolerantlik madaniyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	276
<i>Xidirov Faxriddin Fozilovich</i>	
Транслингвальные практики русскоязычных мигрантов в условиях многоязычной среды	280
<i>Рахмонова Нилуфар Уткир кизи</i>	
Nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalarda leksik-grammatik komponentni diagnostika qilish metodlari	284
<i>Mamatkulova Lobar Tolibjonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida o'yin texnologiyalari asosida bolalarning ta'limiy faoliyatini rivojlantirish.....	288
<i>Norqulova Ma'mura Husniddin qizi</i>	
Nutqdagi fonetik kamchiliklarning o'quv faoliyati va savodxonlikka ta'siri	293
<i>Xikmatova Saboxat Xusniddinovna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda sog'lom psixologik muhitni shakllantirish omillari	296
<i>Xusanbayeva Ziyoda Maxmutdjon qizi</i>	
Social-Psychological Factors of Increasing the Quality of Life	300
<i>Abdullaeva Ranazhon Matyakubovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiruvchi zamonaviy o'quv topshiriqlarini ishlab chiqishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari.....	307
<i>Abdumalikova Gulchiroy</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tayanch hayotiy va fanga oid kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishning didaktik imkoniyatlari.....	311
<i>Adizova Nigora Baxtiyorovna, Sayfullayeva Dilnoza Amrullayevna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ingliz tili darslarida madaniyatlararo kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	316
<i>Azimova Maftuna Azizbekovna</i>	
Talabalarda lingvistik kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	321
<i>Eshbekova Dilnoza Ibraimovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim o'quvchilarida moslashuvchanlikning psixologik xususiyatlari	324
<i>Fayziyeva Gulhayo Erkin qizi, Fatullayeva Manzura Idillo qizi</i>	
Naim Karimov talqinida Oybek badiiy tafakkurining biografik manbalari	327
<i>Jonpo'lotova Gulshoda Qobil qizi</i>	
Kurashchilarning kuch sifatini rivojlantirishda maxsus mashqlardan foydalanish	334
<i>Muxamedjanov Umidulla Fayzullayevich</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda axloqiy idealni shakllantirishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik asoslari	337
<i>Saidova Malika Erkin qizi</i>	
Yengil atletika texnikalarini pedagogik mahoratni rivojlantirish metodikalarida qo'llash	340
<i>Sattarov Qarshiboy Narqulovich, Mirzayev Karim Mamarasul o'g'li</i>	
Yengil atletika mashg'ulotlarida shug'ullanuvchilarning tezkorlik va chidamlilik sifatlarini rivojlantirishning innovatsion metodikasi	344
<i>Sattarov Sardor Sunnatulloevich</i>	
Innovatsion rivojlanish asosida uzluksiz ta'limning integratsiyalashgan mazmunini modellashtirish metodologiyasi.....	348
<i>Umarov Lutfillo Murodilloyevich</i>	
Milliy maktablarda rus tilini o'qitishda raqamli ta'lim resurslari va veb-saytlardan foydalanish metodikasi....	352
<i>Xolmirzayeva Munira Jahongir qizi</i>	
Педагогические основы повышения профессиональной компетентности будущих преподавателей физического воспитания высших образовательных учреждений	357
<i>Мавлянов Бахром Сангирович</i>	
Раннее выявление и мониторинг кожных заболеваний с помощью искусственного интеллекта: интегрированные архитектуры, алгоритмы и перспективы клинического внедрения	361
<i>Э. Ш. Назирова, Ш. Б. Абдусаломова</i>	
Ingliz tilida modallikni ifodalash vositalari va ularning semantik xususiyatlari	368
<i>Abdujalilova Sarvinov Rashid qizi, Abdurazzokova Mehriniso Azimjon qizi</i>	

Ona va farzand munosabatlarida etnomadaniy omillarning psixologik xususiyatlari.....	373
<i>Abdullayeva Dilbar Ubaydullayevna</i>	
O'quvchilarning gapirish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda interaktiv metodlarning o'рни	378
<i>Abdurahmanov Muhammadjon G'ulomjonovich</i>	
Aralash ta'lim texnologiyalari asosida ta'lim jarayonini loyihalashning ilmiy-metodik asoslari.....	381
<i>Alibayev Sobir Xolboyevich</i>	
Formativ baholash jarayonidan foydalanib o'quvchilarning o'rganishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasini oshirish	386
<i>Amirkulova Dilnoza Zokir qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarni kasbiy-pedagogi faoliyatga tayyorlash tendensiyalari	389
<i>Artikbayeva Aziza Abror qizi</i>	
The Role of National Values in English and Uzbek Literature: a Comparative Study	392
<i>Ataniyazova Sohiba Xamidovna</i>	
Frans Kafka ijodining psixologik talqini.....	396
<i>Atayev Shukur-Ali Ayub-Aliyevich</i>	
Development of a Set of Health-Promoting Exercises for Middle-Aged Men 50-60 Years Old, Taking Into Account Physical Training	400
<i>Dehqonova Mahmuda Ortiqovna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda talabalarni jismoniy rivojlantirish metodikalari	404
<i>Imomov Asliddin Abdurazzoqovich, Sattarov Qarshiboy Narqulovich</i>	
Современные мобильные технологии: эволюция и развитие.....	408
<i>Жураев Илхом Исхокович</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda kongruentlik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning mazmuni	413
<i>Kamalova Dilobar Tairovna</i>	
Methodology for Developing Communicative Competence of Future Teachers Based on Multimedia Tools.....	418
<i>Kudratova Sultonposhsha Otabek qizi, Khalilova Mukhlisa Ulug'bek qizi, Ziyotova Umida Otabek qizi</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida ona tili darslarida matn bilan ishlashni tashkil etish.....	423
<i>Erdanova Zamira Olimovna</i>	
Milliy sport turlari orqali talaba yoshlar bilan interfaol dars jarayonini tashkil etish.....	426
<i>Mirzayev Az'am Xudaynazarovich, Sattarov Qarshiboy Narqulovich</i>	
Pedagogika bitiruvchilarining kasbiy o'zini o'zi rivojlantirishga asoslangan barqaror bandligini ta'minlash modeli.....	430
<i>Omonova Mohiniso Maqsud qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda fanlararo integratsiyani sun'iy intellekt asosida takomillashtirishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari.....	435
<i>Panjiyev Jo'raqul Menglimamat o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda web-kvest topshiriqlardan foydalanish.....	440
<i>Saidova Gavhar Ergashovna, Itolmasova Oygul Sabritdinovna</i>	
Developing Communicative Competence in English Language Education Through Modern Interactive Methods.....	443
<i>Sativoldieva Shoxsanam Utkir qizi</i>	

DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE EDUCATION THROUGH MODERN INTERACTIVE METHODS

Satiboldieva Shoxsanam Utkir qizi

Student of Namangan State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: This article discusses the importance of developing communicative competence in English language education through modern interactive methods. In contemporary language teaching, learners are expected not only to master grammar and vocabulary but also to communicate effectively in real-life situations. The paper highlights the role of communicative activities, digital technologies, collaborative learning, and interactive teaching strategies in improving students' speaking abilities and overall communicative competence. Furthermore, the study emphasizes that modern educational technologies and learner-centered approaches increase students' motivation, participation, and critical thinking skills in English language classrooms.

Key words: communicative competence, English language teaching, interactive methods, speaking skills, communicative approach, digital learning, learner-centered education.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tili ta'limida kommunikativ kompetensiyani zamonaviy interaktiv metodlar orqali rivojlantirishning ahamiyati yoritilgan. Zamonaviy til o'qitish jarayonida o'quvchilardan nafaqat grammatika va lug'at boyligini egallash, balki real hayotiy vaziyatlarda samarali muloqot qila olish ham talab etiladi. Maqolada kommunikativ faoliyatlar, raqamli texnologiyalar, hamkorlikda o'qitish hamda interaktiv ta'lim strategiyalarining o'quvchilarning og'zaki nutq ko'nikmalari va umumiy kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, tadqiqotda zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari va o'quvchi markazli yondashuvlar o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasi, faolligi va tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini oshirishi ta'kidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: kommunikativ kompetensiya, ingliz tili ta'limi, interaktiv metodlar, og'zaki nutq ko'nikmalari, kommunikativ yondashuv, raqamli ta'lim, o'quvchi markazli ta'lim.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается важность развития коммуникативной компетенции в обучении английскому языку с помощью современных интерактивных методов. В современном процессе обучения языкам от учащихся требуется не только овладение грамматикой и словарным запасом, но и умение эффективно общаться в реальных жизненных ситуациях. В статье подчеркивается роль коммуникативных заданий, цифровых технологий, совместного обучения и интерактивных стратегий преподавания в развитии навыков устной речи и общей коммуникативной компетенции учащихся. Кроме того, исследование акцентирует внимание на том, что современные образовательные технологии и личностно-ориентированные подходы повышают мотивацию, активность и навыки критического мышления учащихся на уроках английского языка.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативная компетенция, обучение английскому языку, интерактивные методы, навыки устной речи, коммуникативный подход, цифровое обучение, личностно-ориентированное образование.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern educational system, learning foreign languages has become one of the essential components of global communication and professional development. English, as an international language, plays a significant role in education, science, technology, and intercultural communication. Therefore, developing students' communicative competence is considered one of the primary goals of English language teaching. Traditional language teaching methods mainly focused on grammar rules and memorization. However, modern education requires students to use language effectively in authentic communication. As a result, communicative language teaching and interactive methods have become increasingly important in English language classrooms. According to Jalol Jalolov, modern foreign language teaching should develop learners' communicative abilities through practical and interactive activities rather than only grammar instruction. Uzbek methodology

also emphasizes learner-centered education and communicative interaction in language classrooms. Communicative competence refers to the ability to use language appropriately and effectively in different social and cultural contexts. It includes grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence, and strategic competence. Modern interactive methods help learners improve these skills through active participation, collaboration, and meaningful communication.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Background of Communicative Competence

The concept of communicative competence was introduced by the American sociolinguist Dell Hymes in reaction to traditional linguistic theories. According to Hymes, language learning should involve not only grammatical knowledge but also the ability to use language appropriately in social situations. Later, Michael Canale and Merrill Swain expanded the theory and identified four major components of communicative competence:

- grammatical competence;
- sociolinguistic competence;
- discourse competence;
- strategic competence.

These components are interconnected and necessary for successful communication. Modern English language teaching aims to develop all of them through communicative and interactive classroom practices.

Uzbek scholars also pay special attention to communicative approaches in language education. Xoshimov O' and Yoqubov I. emphasize that communicative competence develops effectively when learners participate actively in discussions, role plays, and collaborative speaking activities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on descriptive, comparative, and analytical research methods. The research focuses on the development of communicative competence in English language education through modern interactive methods. Both theoretical and practical aspects of communicative language teaching were examined.

The descriptive method was used to analyze the concept of communicative competence and its main components, including grammatical, sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic competence. The comparative method was applied to evaluate different interactive teaching approaches and their effectiveness in improving learners' communication skills.

The research materials consisted of scientific literature, methodological manuals, academic articles, and studies conducted by both international and Uzbek scholars in the field of English language teaching. Special attention was given to the works of Dell Hymes, Canale and Swain, Jalol Jalolov, Xoshimov, and Yoqubov, who have made significant contributions to communicative language teaching and learner-centered education.

Furthermore, analytical methods were employed to examine the role of communicative activities, collaborative learning, digital technologies, problem-solving tasks, and interactive classroom practices in developing students' communicative competence. The collected information was analyzed and systematized to identify the most effective strategies for enhancing speaking skills, learner participation, critical thinking, and communicative interaction in English language classrooms.

The findings of the study were generalized to provide methodological recommendations for the effective implementation of modern interactive approaches in English language education.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Modern Interactive Methods in English Language Teaching. Communicative Activities

Communicative activities encourage students to use English in meaningful situations. Pair work, group discussions, role plays, interviews, and debates help learners practice real communication and develop fluency. For example, role-playing activities allow students to simulate everyday conversations such as ordering food, attending interviews, or discussing social issues. These tasks improve speaking confidence and communicative strategies.

Collaborative Learning

Collaborative learning creates opportunities for students to work together and exchange ideas. Group projects and peer discussions promote interaction and critical thinking. Students become more active participants in the learning process rather than passive listeners. Moreover, collaborative tasks improve social communication skills and increase learners' motivation. According to Bekmuratova N., interactive methods increase students' classroom participation and help reduce fear of speaking in foreign language learning.

Digital and Interactive Technologies

Modern technologies play a significant role in developing communicative competence. Digital tools such as online platforms, language learning applications, interactive games, and virtual discussions create authentic communication environments.

Applications like:

1. Duolingo,
2. Quizlet,
3. Zoom,
4. Google Classroom

support speaking practice, vocabulary development, and interactive learning. In the post-digital era, students can participate in online discussions, virtual presentations, and international communication projects, which enhance real-world communication skills.

Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking Tasks

Interactive methods also include problem-solving activities and project-based learning. These tasks encourage students to express opinions, negotiate meaning, and think critically in English. For instance, discussing global issues, analyzing media content, or preparing presentations allows learners to use language creatively and meaningfully.

Advantages of Interactive Methods

Modern interactive methods provide several advantages in English language education:

- increase students' motivation and engagement;
- improve speaking fluency and confidence;
- create authentic communication opportunities;
- develop critical thinking and collaboration skills;
- encourage learner autonomy;
- reduce fear of making mistakes.

Interactive learning environments help students become active communicators rather than passive learners. Uzbek pedagogical researchers also note that communicative tasks improve students' independent thinking and creativity in language learning processes.

Challenges in Developing Communicative Competence

Despite the benefits of interactive methods, some challenges still exist. Large classroom sizes, limited technological resources, lack of speaking practice, and students' anxiety may negatively affect communicative development. Additionally, some teachers may continue using teacher-centered methods instead of learner-centered approaches. Therefore, teacher training and methodological support are essential for successful implementation of communicative teaching strategies. According to Saydaliyev S., effective pedagogical technologies and teacher innovation are important factors in improving language teaching quality and communicative learning outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, developing communicative competence is one of the main objectives of modern English language education. Interactive teaching methods, communicative activities, collaborative learning, and digital technologies significantly contribute to improving students' speaking skills and communicative abilities. Modern

English language classrooms should focus on meaningful communication, critical thinking, and learner participation. By integrating innovative and interactive approaches, teachers can create effective learning environments that prepare students for real-life communication in a globalized and post-digital world. Both international and Uzbek methodological studies confirm that communicative and learner-centered approaches positively influence students' oral speech competence and motivation in English language learning.

References:

1. Jalol Jalolov. Chet til o'qitish metodikasi. – Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2012.
2. Xoshimov O'., Yoqubov I. Ingliz tili o'qitish metodikasi. – Toshkent, 2013.
3. Bekmuratova N. Ingliz tilini o'qitishda interfaol metodlardan foydalanish. – Toshkent, 2018.
4. Saydaliyev S. Pedagogik texnologiyalar va pedagogik mahorat. – Toshkent: Innovatsiya, 2019.
5. Tolipov O'., Usmonboyeva M. Pedagogik texnologiyalarning tatbiqiy asoslari. – Toshkent: Fan, 2006.
6. Irisqulov M. Tilshunoslikka kirish. – Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2009.
7. Hymes, D. On Communicative Competence. Oxford University Press, 1972.
8. Canale, M., & Swain, M. Theoretical Bases of Communicative Approaches to Second Language Teaching and Testing. Applied Linguistics, 1980.
9. Richards, J. C. Communicative Language Teaching Today. Cambridge University Press, 2006.
10. Harmer, J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. Pearson Education, 2007.
11. Brown, H. D. Principles of Language Learning and Teaching. Pearson Education, 2000.

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №6(1)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.